

Impact in Production & Operation in Recent Trends in Manufacturing in Tamilnadu Cool Drinks Industry

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Abstract

This paper represent that the cool drinks manufacturing trends in tamilnadu. This paper study the industry new trends in how way attractive to customers . The Maintenance and cover the consumer to our products in valuable service to customers. The producer or manufacture the study of the consumer new technology added to manufacturing the cool drinks item the so many private company to cover the attractive the consumer in cool drinks industry .

Introduction

A product and operation in the cool drinks industry the manufacture handle with the product will produce and rich the consumer a product is the item offered for sale to the consumers in the good service. It can be physical is made at or cyber from every product is made at a cost and added with profit at a price .

A product is something that is produced and sale in large quantities often as a result of a manufacturing process. Try to get the best product at the consumers in high to bootam. (ex) age, Gender, Economily based , Employee .

What is Product and Operation Process

A business or production and operations activities or tasks that product a specific service or product, the process of providing a drink the cool drinks often has six main parts.

1. Design and colors
2. Planning to Size
3. Procurement
4. Production (time)
5. Quality control
6. Packing

New technology can help manufactures reach new markets and create new products however, more companies are still looking for cost – effective ways to develop and test prototypes , and social media and crowd funding may be the solution, most companies already have technologies in place to interact with customers , but crowd funding and social media provides another channel for communication . This communication can be leveraged to gain insight and feedback for new prototypes from consumers and industry experts white in the research and development process, thus , companies can eliminate costs during the design process and deliver an appropriate products in a timely fashion.

Fast-Moving Consumer in Cool Drinks

Products that are sold quickly and of a relatively low cost .

ex : durable goods many fast moving consumer goods have a short shelf life , either as a result of high consumer demand or as the result of fast deterioration . Some F cool drinks , such as meats , fruits, vegetables , dairy products and baked goods are highly perishable other goods such as pre-packaged foods, soft drinks, candies and toiletries have high turnover rates, sales are sometimes influenced by holiday and or seasonal periods and also by the discounts offered

Packaging is critical for cool drinks become successful in the highly dynamic and innovative cool drinks segment, a company not only has to be acquainted with the consumer , brands , and logistics but also it has to have a sound understanding of packaging and product promotion . The packaging has to both hygienic and customers attracting , logistics and distribution systems often require secondary and tertiary packaging to maximize efficiency unit or primary packaging protects products and extents shelf life while providing product information to consumers .

Rural Consumers

Consumers in rural areas typically purchase goods from nearby town and villages, recently , there has been a shift in consumer purchase behavior towards purchasing locally that has prompted the need for better local promotional efforts to generate brand awareness in small towns, cool drinks play a large part in the economy, as in elastic products that touch every part of consumer life in one way or another business that supply cool drinks to a rural community can help provide employment opportunities as well as driving down the cost of such products in those rural areas.

Product & Operation in Consumable to Customers

The cool drinks industry the summer session will produce the huge number of products in market. The multinational company and National cool drinks company to competitor to the market in the offered from price and quality they will survey from producer to the reach the consumer . Consumable goods are used by individuals and business that must be replaced regularly because they wear out or user up. They can also be defined as the components of an end product that is used up or permanently altered in the process of manufacturing such as semiconductors waste and basic chemicals.

Objectives of Product and Operation in Manufacturing Industry

- Planning and implementing manufacturing plans
- Managing projects
- Planning information systems
- Helping to design and develop product and services .
- Managing inventory through the supply chain.
- Managing Delivery to customer in timely manner .

- Optimizing Quality control.
- Conducting procurement / purchasing managing logistics .
- Managing transportation and distribution .
- Managing and maintenances faculties.
- Conducting enterprises resume planning.
- Forecasting for planning.
- Planning for capacity .
- Navigating industrial labour relations.
- Analyzing the value chain.
- Optimizing resource wages .
- Eliminating waste and bottlenecks.
- Continuously improving processes.
- Executing a company's strategic plan.

How way to Avoid the Manufacture the Product Life Cycle in the Maturity and Decline Stage

New product progresses through a sequence of stages from introduction to growth, maturity , and decline . This sequence is know as the product life cycle and is associated with changes in the marketing situation thus impacting the marketing strategy and the marketing mix.

5 Main stages of product life cycle

1. Introduction
2. Growth Stage
3. Maturity Stage
4. Saturation Stage
5. Decline Stage

The Product life cycle is an important concept in marketing it describes the stages a product goes through from what it was first through of unit it finally is removed from the market not all product reach the final stage.

ex Kalimark bovonto first hit the stands in 1958. the company itself completed a century of its existence in 2016.

Manufacture : kali aerated water works

Related Products : Trio Solo fruiters

Introduced : 1958

26 Jan 2017 Bovonto, a grape flavored aerated drink manufactured by kalimark first hit the stand in 1958 the company itself , completed a century of its existence in 2016.

How way avoid to Maturity and Decline

The distinct stages of an industry life cycle are introduction growth maturity and decline , sales typically begin slowly at the introduction phase, then take off rapidly during the growth phase, After leveling out at maturity, sales then begin a gradual decline.

How to Maintain a Strategy in the Decline Stage

Every product goes through the various life cycle phases. The phases a product goes through have a defined series of stages ending in the decline stage of product life cycle theory , products , start out the being introduced growing maturity and decline .

- A market strategy
- Decline strategy
- How to avoid Decline stage

- Marketing strategies
- Advertising marketing strategies

Which analyzing factors contribute to a decrease in sales

- The product
- Marketing
- Technology and Automation
- E- Commerce
- Availability of Finance
- Integration with supplies
- Consumer tastes and expectations
- Economic cycle
- Law and regulations
- Competitors market position the market

Conclusion

Cool drinks consumption is still a controversial issue for public health and public policy over the years, numerous studies have been conducted into the possible links between cool drink in take and medical problems the result of which hover climate changes and consumable person health and suger patent in highly constant.

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